

THE LEVEL OF SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH SKILLS OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS IN AN ACADEMIC RESEARCH

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The Level of Scientific Research Skills of Senior High School Students in an Academic Research

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Abstract

The Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013 (Republic Act No. 10533), the additional two years of Senior High School, aims to broaden the goal of high school education for college preparation. As prescribed by RA 10533, the curriculum shall be relevant, responsive, and research-based. This study aims to determine students' research skills in senior high school through self-assessment in Inquiry-Based Learning. This study utilized a quantitative approach, merging descriptive-comparative and correlational design with 80 respondents from Grade 11 and 12 STEM students. The research utilized an adopted questionnaire by Santiago (2022), composed of 21 items, using the proposed 7-point Likert scale based on mastery classification. The mean score of the level of research skills of Grade 12 ($m=4.97$ $s=.89$) was higher than that of Grade 11 students ($m=4.57$ $s= 1.09$), with a t-test result for the independent sample ($p=0.074$) revealed no significant difference between the mean scores when the group to year level. However, there is a strong direct correlation between academic achievement and level of research skills and vice versa. Conclusively, research training and skills start at the primary level, which translates to the secondary level and reaches the senior high school level as a preparatory stage for college to develop scientific literacy. Thus, initiatives, such as workshops, programs, and developmental training, are recommended for students to enhance their processing and managing skills to enhance and advance their academic research endeavors.

Keywords: *scientific research skills, scientific literacy, inquiry-based learning*

Introduction

The pandemic and its consequences are threatening to undo the progress made on ensuring access to education over the last decades and seriously jeopardizing the chances of achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). UNESCO MGIEP derives its mandate from SDG 4 on quality education and especially from SDG 4.7, which urges governments to equip all learners with “knowledge and skills needed to promote sustainable development.” There is no doubt that the kinds of knowledge and skills required today include not simply classic “job ready” skills but also skills to navigate the rapidly changing, uncertain, and multicultural world, including empathy and emotional resilience. The pandemic provides an opportunity for us all to rethink the purpose of education and reorient curriculum and pedagogy to shape societies where all beings—both human and more than human life—can flourish.

The implementation of the K to 12 Basic Education Program is one of the most significant educational reforms in the country and aims to provide learners with the necessary skills and competence to be globally competitive. One of the necessary skills expected from K-12 graduates is learning and innovation, which will enable the learners to develop creativity, critical thinking, problem-solving, reasoning skills, and curiosity that help learners resolve relevant and timely issues, all reflected in their research output. Stipulated in Republic Act No. 10533, otherwise known as the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013, the additional two years of Senior High School aims to broaden the goal of high school education for college preparation. As prescribed by RA 10533, the curriculum shall be relevant, responsive, and research based. Thus, the basic education is starting to practice and embrace the culture of research (Santiago, 2022).

The empirical nature of science, observation, measurement, experimentation, and scientific method all play a vital role in its progress. The first test of whether an idea is scientific or not is to verify it through an experiment following scientific method. If the idea cannot be tested or verified, it can be classified as unscientific. When it comes to science here in the Philippines, it lags other countries in the world. (Orleans, 2007). This is shown in the 2018 result of the Program for International Students Assessment (PISA) and Trends in International Mathematics and Science Studies (TIMSS) even after implementing the revised basic education curriculum (Diate & Mordeno, 2021). This poor results in student achievement have prompted educational researchers to continue to identify factors that affect the poor achievement of the students. Teacher quality is the most important factor in influencing students' achievement (Orleans, 2007). Their academic preparation and years of experience are some indicators of teachers' quality, in some research those teachers with sufficient academic preparation are seen to be competent in subject matter content and pedagogical skills enabling them to be effective in classrooms and produce larger student achievement gains (Darling-Hammond, 2000). Thus, Research is an important factor in generating knowledge, knowledge, and progress of the human community, and the amount of research done in each community is the index of development of that society (Bicheva, 2017).

According to Cobos-Alvarado et al. (2016), research as a learning process, has been conceived as the result of a process and strategy that could have started to be developed in the first academic year of the students, and not as the culmination of their training. Thus, research training and skills start at the basic level, which translates to secondary level and reach to senior high school level as a preparatory stage to college. It is in SHS that research courses are explicitly introduced to students. In the SHS core curriculum courses, two outcomes provide skills that lead to systematic, in the applied course of the SHS tracks, three courses are dedicated to research this is Practical Research 1, dealing with qualitative research, and Practical Research 2 which trains the student for quantitative research

and Inquires, Investigations and Immersion, on the practical application of research and integrative, scientific, and creative academic manner. In the Science Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) Strand, the students will also have their final research commonly termed as Research capstone requiring students as their outcome a well-written research report (Kuzhabekova & Lee, 2018).

Education should have a dynamic system in which science and research are institutionalized, and research in that position acquires its true position. If so, the curiosity and passion for research in students will be strengthened and potential talents become actual. However, in today's science education and testing system, the application of scientific knowledge is more important and significant. Since students are the main source of knowledge production and are the main assets, they must be properly managed on their knowledge and try to discover hidden assets in their minds so that these treasures become valuable assets (Barber, 2013; Escobar et al., 2018). In order to make decisive role in solving the problems of society and other fields. In the Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) Strand, students will typically culminate their studies with a final research project known as a Research Capstone, which entails the production of a comprehensive research report as their final outcome. However, Santiago (2022), claims that students view research and its process as a requirement for a degree rather than the foundation of their education. Thus, the purpose of this study is to determine the level of student's research skills through self-assessment to know their own perspective of their capabilities.

Research Questions

This research study aims to determine the self-assessment of the students' level of research skills to enhance teaching and learning process. This study sought to find the answer to the following research questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents at SPCP in terms of the following:
 - 1.1. sex;
 - 1.2. age;
 - 1.3. year level; and
 - 1.4. socio economic status?
2. What is the level of Scientific Research Skills of Senior High School Students?
3. Is there a significant difference between the levels of scientific research skills when grouped according to grade level?
4. Is there a significant correlation between the mean scores of the level of research skills and student's academic performance?

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized a quantitative approach conducted in Saint Paul College Paranaque, specifically descriptive-comparative and correlational design. It aims to describe the situation and nature of the respondents under study and apply statistical treatment to interpret the data. Data from the survey were collected by administering research questionnaires to determine the level of research skills of the students.

The study was conducted among Grade 11 and Grade 12 STEM students using random sampling. A descriptive-comparative method was employed to determine students' level of research skills and when compared to age level. Meanwhile, the correlation was used to determine relationship between two variables.

Respondents

The study respondents were from the Senior High School Department of Grade 11 and Grade 12 from Saint Paul College Paranaque. The research respondents are under the STEM track: 40 students from Grade 11 St. Mark and 40 from Grade 12 St. Luke who were randomly selected.

Instruments

The research utilized an adopted questionnaire by Santiago (2022), composed of a total of 21 items, as divided into three: Five (5) for the SRPS placed as questions 1 to 5 respectively; Eight (8) items for the SRMS placed as questions 6 to 13; Lastly, seven (7) items for SIDS placed as questions 14 to 20.

The final instrument was developed using the proposed 7-point Likert scale based on mastery classification, where 7= "Mastered", 6= "Closely Approximating Mastery", 5= "Moving Towards Mastery", 4="Average", 3="Low", 2= "Very Low", and 1- "Absolutely No Mastery". The research instruments used a three-stage content validation process by the two experts, adequate factorial analysis result using exploratory factor analysis, and reliability testing for both internal consistency and test re-test analysis together with the subsequent concurrent criterion-related validity, thus providing adequate information on the validity, reliability, and factor structure of the instrument.

Procedure

The researcher sought permission from the University President and Principal of the Basic Education Department of SPCP through a

letter informing them about the participation of the students in the data collection. Upon the principal's approval, the researcher conferred with the subject teacher on the data gathering schedule, particularly administering the questionnaires to the students. At the same time, the researcher sought collaboration and permission with the subject teacher to collect the students' grades to be included in the study. Students' consent is stipulated in Google forms, indicating the strict adherence to the Data Privacy Act of 2012, which is also administered to the participating students, stating that the participation and data gathered in the study will be treated with the utmost confidentiality. Informed consent from the respondents was likewise sought to ensure that the study conforms to the ethical norms of research. The Google forms was used for the administration of questionnaires. After floating the questionnaire, the data was tallied and interpreted.

Data Analysis

Mean and standard deviation were used to determine student's level of research skills. The researcher utilized t- test for independent sample in comparing two independent group to determine if there is a significant difference between the level of research skills when group according to year level. Pearson r was also used to find the correlation between students' scientific research skills and academic achievement using an adopted instrument validated and developed by Santiago (2022)

Ethical Considerations

In this study, it is essential to observe ethical standards and considerations before, during, and after the conduct of the study. The study's respondents can ensure that the data and information are taken with the utmost confidentiality. Thus, the researcher assures that there will be no bias or assumption before the results unless proven by valid and reliable data. The adherence to the Republic Act 10173, known as the Data Privacy Act of 2012, will be strictly observed. Such that respondents should be anonymous, and the data gathered will be taken with the utmost confidentiality. Codes will protect personal data; only the researcher can access it. All data gathered will be strictly used during the duration of the study and will be deleted once it is over. Before participating, all respondents participating in this study will sign the informed consent form, which includes the study's purpose and benefits. The respondents have all the right to decline or participate in the study. Their participation is voluntary, and their data will be kept private. At all costs, the researcher must uphold honesty, respect, and a sense of responsibility towards the respondents, users, area, and the community involved in the research process. The study's integrity will not be compromised since the researcher has no personal 14 gain from conducting it. This study has no conflict of interest, as stated by the researcher. At the study's end, the researcher will co-own the result and the University School of Graduate Studies.

Results and Discussion

This section comprises the tables for the study's specific self-related perceptions profile variables. It includes three tables, Tables 1 to 3, with the essential information about the respondents' self-concept, self-esteem, and self-efficacy. These were utilized to describe the respondents' self-related perceptions.

Table 1. *Sex of the Respondents*

<i>Sex</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
Female	48	60%
Male	32	40%
Total	80	100%

Table 2. *Age Distribution of the Respondents*

<i>Year Level</i>	<i>mean</i>	<i>SD</i>
15-19	17.32	0.0808

Table 3. *Year Level Distribution*

<i>Year Level</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
Grade 12	40	50%
Grade 11	40	50%
Total	80	100%

Table 4. *Socio Economic Status of the Respondents*

<i>Socio Economic Status</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
31k- above	24	30%
21k-30k	9	11.2%
11k-20k	8	10%
10k- below	39	48.8%
Total	80	100%

Table 5. *Self-assessment of Students' Level of Scientific Research Skills*

	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
Very Low	2	2.5
Low	3	3.8
Average	29	36.2
Moving towards mastery	23	28.8
Closely approximating mastery	19	23.8
Mastered	4	5.0
Total	80	100.0

Mean: 4.73 (Moving Towards mastery) SD:1

Table 6. *Mean, Standard Deviation and Qualitative Description of each statement*

<i>Statements</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>
I can appropriately analyze main ideas of a varied data source such as literature and my own experiment.	4.6750	1.17759	Moving Towards Mastery
I can discuss data interpretation from different data sources such as literature and my own experiment.	4.6500	1.22319	Moving Towards Mastery
I can appropriately use statistical procedures in my analysis.	4.3875	1.17456	Average
I can choose reliable information from varied data sources.	5.4250	1.25057	Moving Towards Mastery
I can appropriately use scientific procedures in implementing experiments.	4.7250	1.25259	Moving Towards Mastery
I can manage research articles of a theme drawn from scientific journals, databases, etc.	4.7000	1.34447	Moving Towards Mastery
I can recognize a scientific paper in reputable resources.	4.6625	1.34958	Moving Towards Mastery
I can communicate orally or written the results of a review of scientific literature.	4.6500	1.31303	Moving Towards Mastery
I can identify gaps in the articles I read from literatures and related studies.	4.5500	1.33027	Moving Towards Mastery
I can systematically plan research and its implementation based on scientific rules.	4.4750	1.19042	Average
I can appropriately organize the structure of data analysis based on scientific rules.	4.5625	1.23087	Moving Towards Mastery
I can systematically manage the actual study or experimentation implementation	4.5250	1.33098	Moving Towards Mastery
I can systematically manage the actual research writing.	4.6250	1.28649	Moving Towards Mastery
I can develop my own scientific inquiry or question based on data available at hand that are scientifically correct.	4.7000	1.25688	Moving Towards Mastery
I can prepare an abstract of a research topic.	4.8875	1.28274	Moving Towards Mastery
I can bring my ideas in developing a research topic.	5.0250	1.30214	Moving Towards Mastery
I can create my own hypothesis	4.9500	1.22112	Average
I can create correct recommendations based on the result of my own study.	5.1000	1.15397	Moving Towards Mastery
I can create appropriate rationale of my study.	4.5875	1.08725	Moving Towards Mastery
I can make correctly create my own conclusions.	5.1625	1.16319	Moving Towards Mastery
Mean	4.7256	1.00694	Moving Towards Mastery

Table 7. *Significant Difference between the Mean Score of Research skills when grouped according to Year Level*

<i>Year level</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Sig. (2- tailed)</i>
Grade 11	40	4.5650	1.08918	-1.812	78	.074
Grade 12	40	4.9688	.89369	-1.812		

Table 8. *Significant Correlation Between the Mean Scores of the Level of Research Skills and Student's Academic Performance*

		<i>Academic Achievement</i>	<i>Level of Research Skills</i>
Academic Achievement	Pearson Correlation	1	.881**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	80	80
Level of Research Skill	Pearson Correlation	.881**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	80	80

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Table 1 above shows the distribution of respondents in terms of sex. The data revealed more female (60%) respondents than male (40%) respondents. The age distribution of the respondents ranges from 15-19 years old, with an equivalent average of 17.32 (SD= 0.808). The data revealed that most respondents are under the current educational range system in the Philippines and are expected to be senior high school students. Table 3 shows approximately equal numbers of STEM respondents in Grade 11 (50%) and Grade 12 (50%). As shown in Table 4, the socio-economic status of the respondents and most of the respondents (48.8%) falls under the range of a monthly family income of 10,000 – below. According to the Philippine Institute of Development Studies, a family income of less than P9,520 is classified under the poverty threshold, which is poor. Significantly, 10% of the respondents with a family income under 11,000 pesos -20,000 pesos were classified as low income. There were 11.2% of the respondents with a monthly family income of 21,000 –30,000 classified as lower middle-income, and 30 % among respondents with a monthly income of 31,000 pesos and above classified as middle-income.

As shown in Table 5, the respondents' research skills vary from very low (2.5%) to mastered (5.0%). Most of the respondents are under average level (36.3%) based on self-assessment. However, the overall mean falls under moving towards mastery (4.73) with a standard deviation of 1.007, which contradicts the highest percentage level considering how varied the shown data is.

Table 6 shows the average students' self-assessment of their research skills. Most of the respondents assessed themselves as moving towards Mastery in the majority of the statements except S3 (I can appropriately use statistical procedures in my analysis) and S10 (I can systematically plan research and its implementation based on scientific rules), which are at an average level. Studies show that research on the teaching and learning of statistics remains disconnected, fragmented, and difficult to access. However, various literature reviews firm the importance of statistics and its application in different fields of expertise (Zieffler et al., 2008). The overall perception of Students' research skills is 4.73 with a standard deviation of 1.007, which is assessed to be moving towards mastery.

As gleaned in Table 7, the mean score of the level of research skills of Grade 12 ($m=4.97$ $s=.89$) was higher than that of Grade 11 students ($m=4.57$ $s= 1.09$). However, the t-test result for the independent sample ($p=0.074$) reveals no significant difference between the mean scores when the group to year level. The results indicate that the research skills of Grade 11 and Grade 12 are approximately the same.

As shown in Table 8, there is a strong direct correlation between academic achievement and level of research skills and vice versa. It reveals that as the level of research skills improves, the higher the chance of getting excellent grades, and the higher the academic achievement, the more mastered the students are in doing research.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn: This study shows that the overall self-assessment of students' scientific research skills, which is assessed to be moving toward mastery, is sufficient. However, the data reveals that Statement 3 (I can appropriately use statistical procedures in my analysis) under Scientific Research Processing Skills and S10 (I can systematically plan research and its implementation based on scientific rules) under Scientific Research Managing Skills are the lowest, which are in average level. Therefore, the students' scientific research skills are greatly influenced by how they process and manage the data.

The self-assessment of the student's scientific research skills is not directly related to grade level, especially since there is a small gap between grade 11 and grade 12. However, a positive relationship exists between the students' scientific research skills and Academic achievement. Various literature supports that researchers' qualifications, such as skills and academic characteristics, are predictive factors for research productivity; as an individual increases qualifications, research productivity elevates (Atieno et al., 2021). Thus, scientific research skills help students enhance academic achievement, especially in science.

The researcher would also like to make recommendations to the following stakeholders. To the Administration, this study will help benefit SPCP in the Personnel Development and School improvement especially embracing the culture of research and research exposure not only local but international conferences starting from the basic level to help students engage in the scientific process, and foster curiosity, problem- solving, and critical thinking. To the teachers, to initiate mentorship programs, workshop and activities on sustaining students' eagerness and motivation in doing research and its impact to various field. To the students, to look further into this study as a basis for understanding the implication of how scientific research skills improve various field. To the future researchers to use this as a basis of improvement or a guide to future studies regarding on sustaining scientific research skills and motivation to quality research production non only in the field of science but also considering large scope. The researcher also recommends that future researchers investigate using digital tools, applications, and technology in research activities, providing opportunities for students to enhance their ability to collect, analyze, and communicate the findings effectively. Jamovi and SPSS applications are effective ways to help students enhance their processing and managing skills to advance their academic careers. Thus, workshops on how to navigate these applications are highly recommended.

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